

Supplementary Search history 10 May 2023 (Medline, Embase, PsycInfo, and Scopus).

Medline

#	Query	Results from 10 May 2023
1	laminectomy.mp. or exp Laminectomy/	16,549
2	exp Diskectomy, Percutaneous/ or exp Diskectomy/ or discectom*.mp. or diskectom*.mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	11,661
3	exp Decompression, Surgical/ or (surg* adj3 decompression*).mp.	41,029
4	(spin* adj3 fusion*).mp. or exp Spinal Fusion/	36,053
5	exp Spinal Diseases/su	45,174
6	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5	97,913
7	neurosurgery.mp. or exp Neurosurgery/	38,599
8	(neurosurgical adj3 procedure*).mp. or exp Neurosurgical Procedures/	215,394
9	orthop?edic*.mp. or exp Orthopedics/	144,920
10	exp Orthopedic Procedures/	357,387
11	(spin* adj3 surg*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	31,522
12	(low adj3 back adj3 pain).mp. or exp Low Back Pain/ or (back adj3 pain).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading	76,166

	word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	
13	radicul*.mp. or exp Radiculopathy/	21,263
14	(spin* adj3 disease*).mp. or exp Spinal Diseases/	157,052
15	spine.mp. or exp Spine/ or (spin* adj3 column*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	249,873
16	(lumbar adj3 vertebra*).mp. or exp Lumbar Vertebrae/	66,171
17	12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16	384,399
18	((spine* or spinal* or lumbar*) adj7 (surg* or neurosurg* or orthop?ed*)).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	57,953
19	telemedicine*.mp. or exp Telemedicine/ or telehealth*.mp. or tele-health*.mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	58,601
20	telephone*.mp. or exp Telephone/ or (cell adj3 phone*).mp. or exp Cell Phone/ or	104,959

	(mobile adj3 phone*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	
21	(smartphone* or smart-phone*).mp. or exp Smartphone/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	25,103
22	tablet*.mp. or exp Tablets/	69,969
23	(mobile adj3 application*).mp. or exp Mobile Applications/	16,546
24	(tele-rehabilitation* or telerehabilitation* or (tele adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Telerehabilitation/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	2,406
25	telenurs*.mp. or exp Telenursing/	478
26	((video adj3 conf*) or video-conf* or videoconf*).mp. or exp Videoconferencing/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms,	7,612

	population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	
27	(health adj3 communica*).mp. or exp Health Communication/ or (medic* adj3 inform*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	64,442
28	(inform* adj3 communicat* adj3 techn*).mp. or exp Medical Informatics Applications/ or (medical* adj3 informatic*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	501,752
29	(informatic* adj3 application*).mp.	3,105
30	((health adj3 inform* adj3 techn*) or (nurs* adj3 inform*)).mp. or exp Nursing Informatics/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	13,813
31	((electronic adj3 health adj3 service*) or ehealth or e-health).mp. adj5 (communicat*.mp. or exp Communication/) [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary	1,332

	concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	
32	((home adj3 visit*) or (house adj3 call*)).mp. or exp House Calls/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	15,136
33	(real-time adj3 support*).mp.	1,082
34	((after adj3 car*) or after-car*).mp. or exp Aftercare/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	368,495
35	((continuo* adj3 nurs*) or (followup adj3 car*) or (follow-up adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	27,214
36	((followup adj3 support*) or (follow-up adj3 support*)).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population	2,805

	supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	
37	(remote adj3 monitor*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	6,223
38	(active adj3 post-discharge adj3 surveillanc*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	9
39	simulation*.mp. or exp Simulation Training/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	624,179
40	((instruction* adj3 film*) or (instruction* adj3 video*)).mp. or exp "Instructional Film and Video"/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	1,540
41	exp Pain Management/ or (pain adj3 manag*).mp. or exp Analgesia/ or	157,511

	analgesia*.mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	
42	(clinic* adj3 teach* adj3 method*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	369
43	((client* adj3 educat*) or (patient* adj3 educat*)).mp. or exp Patient Education as Topic/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	129,545
44	(car* adj3 behavior*).mp. or exp Continuity of Patient Care/ or (patient* adj3 car*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	985,654
45	(self-car* or (self adj3 car*)).mp. or exp Self Care/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word,	88,532

	keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	
46	(health adj3 promot*).mp. or exp Health Promotion/	140,273
47	((multi-disciplin* adj3 car*) or (multidisciplin* adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	11,997
48	(self-manag* or (self adj3 manag*)).mp. or exp Self-Management/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	32,514
49	recover*.mp. or exp Recovery of Function/	840,101
50	convalescence.mp. or exp Convalescence/ or exp Rehabilitation/ or rehab*.mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	619,978
51	(mobile adj3 team\$).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading	1,034

	word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	
52	(text adj3 messag*).mp. or exp Text Messaging/	8,204
53	((pre-operative adj3 educat*) or (preoperative adj3 educat*) or ((preoperative adj3 exercise*) or prehabilitation*).mp. or exp Preoperative Exercise/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	2,939
54	((emotional adj3 adjust*) or (psychologic* adj3 adjust*) or (adapt* adj3 psychologic*) or (adapt* adj3 physiologic*) or (physiologic* adj3 adjust*).mp. or Adaptation, Psychological/ or Adaptation, Physiological/ or (adaptive adj3 behavior*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	200,188
55	((short adj3 time adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 term adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 time adj3 hospitalization*) or (short adj3 term adj3 hospitalization*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique	1,052

	identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	
56	(return* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	4,884
57	(hospital* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	14,572
58	discharg*.mp. or exp Patient Discharge/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	341,855
59	(postdischarg* or (post adj3 discharg*) or post-discharg*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	15,320
60	(transition* adj3 home*).mp.	1,639
61	(length* adj3 stay*).mp. or exp Length of Stay/	168,697

62	7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11	680,411
63	17 and 62	88,783
64	6 or 18 or 63	146,710
65	19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 or 53 or 54	4,019,338
66	((postoperativ* adj3 rehabilitation*) or (postoperativ* adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	4,560
67	55 or 56 or 57 or 58 or 59 or 60 or 61 or 66	496,364
68	64 and 65 and 67	3,284
69	limit 68 to (danish or english or norwegian or swedish)	3,100
70	limit 69 to yr="2022 - 2023"	430

laminectomy.mp. or exp Laminectomy/
exp Discectomy, Percutaneous/ or exp Discectomy/ or discectom*.mp. or discectom*.mp.
[mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]
exp Decompression, Surgical/ or (surg* adj3 decompression*).mp.
(spin* adj3 fusion*).mp. or exp Spinal Fusion/
exp Spinal Diseases/su
1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5
neurosurgery.mp. or exp Neurosurgery/
(neurosurgical adj3 procedure*).mp. or exp Neurosurgical Procedures/
orthop?edic*.mp. or exp Orthopedics/
exp Orthopedic Procedures/
(spin* adj3 surg*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]
(low adj3 back adj3 pain).mp. or exp Low Back Pain/ or (back adj3 pain).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word,

keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

radicul*.mp. or exp Radiculopathy/
 (spin* adj3 disease*).mp. or exp Spinal Diseases/
 spine.mp. or exp Spine/ or (spin* adj3 column*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(lumbar adj3 vertebra*).mp. or exp Lumbar Vertebrae/
 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16
 ((spine* or spinal* or lumbar*) adj7 (surg* or neurosurg* or orthop?ed*)).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

telemedicine*.mp. or exp Telemedicine/ or telehealth*.mp. or tele-health*.mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

telephone*.mp. or exp Telephone/ or (cell adj3 phone*).mp. or exp Cell Phone/ or (mobile adj3 phone*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(smartphone* or smart-phone*).mp. or exp Smartphone/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

tablet*.mp. or exp Tablets/
 (mobile adj3 application*).mp. or exp Mobile Applications/
 (tele-rehabilitation* or telerehabilitation* or (tele adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Telerehabilitation/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

telenurs*.mp. or exp Telenursing/
 ((video adj3 conf* or video-conf* or videoconf*).mp. or exp Videoconferencing/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(health adj3 communica*).mp. or exp Health Communication/ or (medic* adj3 inform*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating

sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word] (inform* adj3 communicat* adj3 techn*).mp. or exp Medical Informatics Applications/ or (medical* adj3 informatic*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word] (informatic* adj3 application*).mp.

((health adj3 inform* adj3 techn*) or (nurs* adj3 inform*)).mp. or exp Nursing Informatics/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word] ((electronic adj3 health adj3 service*) or ehealth or e-health).mp. adj5 (communicat*.mp. or exp Communication/) [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

((home adj3 visit*) or (house adj3 call*)).mp. or exp House Calls/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word] (real-time adj3 support*).mp.

((after adj3 car*) or after-car*).mp. or exp Aftercare/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

((continuo* adj3 nurs*) or (followup adj3 car*) or (follow-up adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

((followup adj3 support*) or (follow-up adj3 support*)).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(remote adj3 monitor*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(active adj3 post-discharge adj3 surveillanc*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name

of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

simulation*.mp. or exp Simulation Training/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

((instruction* adj3 film*) or (instruction* adj3 video*)).mp. or exp "Instructional Film and Video"/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

exp Pain Management/ or (pain adj3 manag*).mp. or exp Analgesia/ or analgesia*.mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(clinic* adj3 teach* adj3 method*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

((client* adj3 educat*) or (patient* adj3 educat*)).mp. or exp Patient Education as Topic/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(car* adj3 behavior*).mp. or exp Continuity of Patient Care/ or (patient* adj3 car*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(self-car* or (self adj3 car*)).mp. or exp Self Care/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(health adj3 promot*).mp. or exp Health Promotion/

((multi-disciplin* adj3 car*) or (multidisciplin* adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(self-manag* or (self adj3 manag*)).mp. or exp Self-Management/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare

disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

recover*.mp. or exp Recovery of Function/

convalescence.mp. or exp Convalescence/ or exp Rehabilitation/ or rehab*.mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(mobile adj3 team\$).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(text adj3 messag*).mp. or exp Text Messaging/

((pre-operative adj3 educat*) or (preoperative adj3 educat*) or ((preoperative adj3 exercise*) or prehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Preoperative Exercise/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

((emotional adj3 adjust*) or (psychologic* adj3 adjust*) or (adapt* adj3 psychologic*) or (adapt* adj3 physiologic*) or (physiologic* adj3 adjust*)).mp. or Adaptation, Psychological/ or Adaptation, Physiological/ or (adaptive adj3 behavior*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

((short adj3 time adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 term adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 time adj3 hospitalization*) or (short adj3 term adj3 hospitalization*)).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(return* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(hospital* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

discharg*.mp. or exp Patient Discharge/ [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(postdischarg* or (post adj3 discharg*) or post-discharg*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

(transition* adj3 home*).mp.

(length* adj3 stay*).mp. or exp Length of Stay/

7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11

17 and 62

6 or 18 or 63

19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 or 53 or 54

((postoperativ* adj3 rehabilitation*) or (post-operativ* adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

55 or 56 or 57 or 58 or 59 or 60 or 61 or 66

64 and 65 and 67

limit 68 to (danish or english or norwegian or swedish)

limit 69 to yr="2022 - 2023"

<https://proxy1->

[bib.sdu.dk:2048/login?url=https://ovidsp.ovid.com/ovidweb.cgi?T=JS&NEWS=N&PAGE=main&SHAREDSEARCHID=1BA77QwmMQFUk81YVoLme0vkIOkhVAR8n9WSTRf2NtgiBMY1LfUzDnyaDT47Ji1dB](https://proxy1-bib.sdu.dk:2048/login?url=https://ovidsp.ovid.com/ovidweb.cgi?T=JS&NEWS=N&PAGE=main&SHAREDSEARCHID=1BA77QwmMQFUk81YVoLme0vkIOkhVAR8n9WSTRf2NtgiBMY1LfUzDnyaDT47Ji1dB)

Embase

Link:

[Click to run search](#)

The above Jumpstart will only work for users who have access to this specific database.

Database:

Embase Classic+Embase <1947 to 2023 May 09>

#	Query	Results from 10 May 2023
1	laminectomy.mp. or exp Laminectomy/	30,533
2	exp Diskectomy, Percutaneous/ or exp Diskectomy/ or discectom*.mp. or diskectom*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	17,937
3	exp Decompression, Surgical/ or (surg* adj3 decompression*).mp.	69,780
4	(spin* adj3 fusion*).mp. or exp Spinal Fusion/	44,099
5	exp Spinal Diseases/su	59,132
6	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5	169,032
7	neurosurgery.mp. or exp Neurosurgery/	354,170
8	(neurosurgical adj3 procedure*).mp. or exp Neurosurgical Procedures/	343,179
9	orthop?edic*.mp. or exp Orthopedics/	208,822
10	exp Orthopedic Procedures/	632,085
11	(spin* adj3 surg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	60,263
12	(low adj3 back adj3 pain).mp. or exp Low Back Pain/ or (back adj3 pain).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	119,851

13	radicul*.mp. or exp Radiculopathy/	60,593
14	(spin* adj3 disease*).mp. or exp Spinal Diseases/	339,741
15	spine.mp. or exp Spine/ or (spin* adj3 column*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	421,993
16	(lumbar adj3 vertebra*).mp. or exp Lumbar Vertebrae/	35,229
17	12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16	679,589
18	((spine* or spinal* or lumbar*) adj7 (surg* or neurosurg* or orthop?ed*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	113,112
19	telemedicine*.mp. or exp Telemedicine/ or telehealth*.mp. or tele-health*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	93,140
20	telephone*.mp. or exp Telephone/ or (cell adj3 phone*).mp. or exp Cell Phone/ or (mobile adj3 phone*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	166,943
21	(smartphone* or smart-phone*).mp. or exp Smartphone/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	37,024
22	tablet*.mp. or exp Tablets/	130,326
23	(mobile adj3 application*).mp. or exp Mobile Applications/	28,127
24	(tele-rehabilitation* or telerehabilitation* or (tele adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Telerehabilitation/ [mp=title, abstract,	3,286

	heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	
25	telenurs*.mp. or exp Telenursing/	555
26	((video adj3 conf*) or video-conf* or videoconf*).mp. or exp Videoconferencing/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	12,432
27	(health adj3 communica*).mp. or exp Health Communication/ or (medic* adj3 inform*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	182,146
28	(inform* adj3 communicat* adj3 techn*).mp. or exp Medical Informatics Applications/ or (medical* adj3 informatic*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	31,390
29	(informatic* adj3 application*).mp.	712
30	((health adj3 inform* adj3 techn*) or (nurs* adj3 inform*)).mp. or exp Nursing Informatics/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	15,823
31	((electronic adj3 health adj3 service*) or ehealth or e-health).mp. adj5 (communicat*.mp. or exp Communication/) [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	1,329
32	((home adj3 visit*) or (house adj3 call*)).mp. or exp House Calls/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title,	19,991

	device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	
33	(real-time adj3 support*).mp.	1,485
34	((after adj3 car*) or after-car*).mp. or exp Aftercare/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	2,278,729
35	((continuo* adj3 nurs*) or (followup adj3 car*) or (follow-up adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	44,862
36	((followup adj3 support*) or (follow-up adj3 support*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	4,506
37	(remote adj3 monitor*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	9,966
38	(active adj3 post-discharge adj3 surveillanc*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	16
39	simulation*.mp. or exp Simulation Training/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	642,231
40	((instruction* adj3 film*) or (instruction* adj3 video*)).mp. or exp "Instructional Film and Video"/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device	2,434

	trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	
41	exp Pain Management/ or (pain adj3 manag*).mp. or exp Analgesia/ or analgesia*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	279,311
42	(clinic* adj3 teach* adj3 method*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	632
43	((client* adj3 educat*) or (patient* adj3 educat*)).mp. or exp Patient Education as Topic/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	171,760
44	(car* adj3 behavior*).mp. or exp Continuity of Patient Care/ or (patient* adj3 car*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	1,842,578
45	(self-car* or (self adj3 car*)).mp. or exp Self Care/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	126,285
46	(health adj3 promot*).mp. or exp Health Promotion/	168,484
47	((multi-disciplin* adj3 car*) or (multidisciplin* adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	20,251
48	(self-manag* or (self adj3 manag*)).mp. or exp Self-Management/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title,	118,954

	device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	
49	recover*.mp. or exp Recovery of Function/	1,150,437
50	convalescence.mp. or exp Convalescence/ or exp Rehabilitation/ or rehab*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	820,301
51	(mobile adj3 team\$).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	1,660
52	(text adj3 messag*).mp. or exp Text Messaging/	11,569
53	((pre-operative adj3 educat*) or (preoperative adj3 exercis*) or (preoperative adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Preoperative Exercise/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	5,130
54	((emotional adj3 adjust*) or (psychologic* adj3 adjust*) or (adapt* adj3 psychologic*) or (adapt* adj3 physiologic*) or (physiologic* adj3 adjust*)).mp. or Adaptation, Psychological/ or Adaptation, Physiological/ or (adaptive adj3 behavior*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	81,455
55	((short adj3 time adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 term adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 time adj3 hospitalization*) or (short adj3 term adj3 hospitalization*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word,	1,704

	floating subheading word, candidate term word]	
56	(return* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	7,710
57	(hospital* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	20,203
58	discharg*.mp. or exp Patient Discharge/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	641,352
59	(postdischarg* or (post adj3 discharg*) or post-discharg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	29,144
60	(transition* adj3 home*).mp.	2,407
61	(length* adj3 stay*).mp. or exp Length of Stay/	317,296
62	7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11	1,045,087
63	17 and 62	162,374
64	6 or 18 or 63	266,993
65	19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 or 53 or 54	6,994,502
66	((postoperativ* adj3 rehabilitation*) or (post-operativ* adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	6,155
67	55 or 56 or 57 or 58 or 59 or 60 or 61 or 66	918,405

68	64 and 65 and 67	11,484
69	limit 68 to (danish or english or norwegian or swedish)	11,064
70	limit 69 to (article or article in press or books or chapter or conference paper or "conference review" or editorial or erratum or letter or note or "preprint (unpublished, non-peer reviewed)" or "review" or short survey or tombstone)	8,160
71	limit 70 to yr="2022 - 2023"	1,431

laminectomy.mp. or exp Laminectomy/
exp Discectomy, Percutaneous/ or exp Discectomy/ or discectom*.mp. or discectom*.mp.
[mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug
manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term
word]

exp Decompression, Surgical/ or (surg* adj3 decompression*).mp.
(spin* adj3 fusion*).mp. or exp Spinal Fusion/
exp Spinal Diseases/su
1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5
neurosurgery.mp. or exp Neurosurgery/
(neurosurgical adj3 procedure*).mp. or exp Neurosurgical Procedures/
orthop?edic*.mp. or exp Orthopedics/
exp Orthopedic Procedures/
(spin* adj3 surg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device
manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading
word, candidate term word]

(low adj3 back adj3 pain).mp. or exp Low Back Pain/ or (back adj3 pain).mp. [mp=title, abstract,
heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade
name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

radicul*.mp. or exp Radiculopathy/
(spin* adj3 disease*).mp. or exp Spinal Diseases/
spine.mp. or exp Spine/ or (spin* adj3 column*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade
name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading
word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

(lumbar adj3 vertebra*).mp. or exp Lumbar Vertebrae/
12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16
((spine* or spinal* or lumbar*) adj7 (surg* or neurosurg* or orthop?ed*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract,
heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade
name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

telemedicine*.mp. or exp Telemedicine/ or telehealth*.mp. or tele-health*.mp. [mp=title, abstract,
heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade
name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

telephone*.mp. or exp Telephone/ or (cell adj3 phone*).mp. or exp Cell Phone/ or (mobile adj3
phone*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer,
drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate

term word]
 (smartphone* or smart-phone*).mp. or exp Smartphone/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
 tablet*.mp. or exp Tablets/
 (mobile adj3 application*).mp. or exp Mobile Applications/
 (tele-rehabilitation* or telerehabilitation* or (tele adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Telerehabilitation/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
 telenurs*.mp. or exp Telenursing/
 ((video adj3 conf*) or video-conf* or videoconf*).mp. or exp Videoconferencing/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
 (health adj3 communica*).mp. or exp Health Communication/ or (medic* adj3 inform*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
 (inform* adj3 communicat* adj3 techn*).mp. or exp Medical Informatics Applications/ or (medical* adj3 informatic*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
 (informatic* adj3 application*).mp.
 ((health adj3 inform* adj3 techn*) or (nurs* adj3 inform*)).mp. or exp Nursing Informatics/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
 ((electronic adj3 health adj3 service*) or ehealth or e-health).mp. adj5 (communicat*.mp. or exp Communication/) [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
 ((home adj3 visit*) or (house adj3 call*)).mp. or exp House Calls/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
 (real-time adj3 support*).mp.
 ((after adj3 car*) or after-car*).mp. or exp Aftercare/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
 ((continuo* adj3 nurs*) or (followup adj3 car*) or (follow-up adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
 ((followup adj3 support*) or (follow-up adj3 support*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
 (remote adj3 monitor*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
 (active adj3 post-discharge adj3 surveillanc*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade

name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

simulation*.mp. or exp Simulation Training/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

((instruction* adj3 film*) or (instruction* adj3 video*)).mp. or exp "Instructional Film and Video"/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

exp Pain Management/ or (pain adj3 manag*).mp. or exp Analgesia/ or analgesia*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

(clinic* adj3 teach* adj3 method*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

((client* adj3 educat*) or (patient* adj3 educat*)).mp. or exp Patient Education as Topic/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

(car* adj3 behavior*).mp. or exp Continuity of Patient Care/ or (patient* adj3 car*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

(self-car* or (self adj3 car*)).mp. or exp Self Care/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

(health adj3 promot*).mp. or exp Health Promotion/

((multi-disciplin* adj3 car*) or (multidisciplin* adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

(self-manag* or (self adj3 manag*)).mp. or exp Self-Management/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

recover*.mp. or exp Recovery of Function/

convalescence.mp. or exp Convalescence/ or exp Rehabilitation/ or rehab*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

(mobile adj3 team\$).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

(text adj3 messag*).mp. or exp Text Messaging/

((pre-operative adj3 educat*) or (preoperative adj3 educat*) or ((preoperative adj3 exercise*) or prehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Preoperative Exercise/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

((emotional adj3 adjust*) or (psychologic* adj3 adjust*) or (adapt* adj3 psychologic*) or (adapt* adj3 physiologic*) or (physiologic* adj3 adjust*)).mp. or Adaptation, Psychological/ or Adaptation, Physiological/ or (adaptive adj3 behavior*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]

((short adj3 time adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 term adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 time adj3 hospitalization*) or (short adj3 term adj3 hospitalization*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
(return* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
(hospital* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
discharg*.mp. or exp Patient Discharge/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
(postdischarg* or (post adj3 discharg*) or post-discharg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
(transition* adj3 home*).mp.
(length* adj3 stay*).mp. or exp Length of Stay/
7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11
17 and 62
6 or 18 or 63
19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 or 53 or 54
((postoperativ* adj3 rehabilitation*) or (post-operativ* adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
55 or 56 or 57 or 58 or 59 or 60 or 61 or 66
64 and 65 and 67
limit 68 to (danish or english or norwegian or swedish)
limit 69 to (article or article in press or books or chapter or conference paper or "conference review" or editorial or erratum or letter or note or "preprint (unpublished, non-peer reviewed)" or "review" or short survey or tombstone)
limit 70 to yr="2022 - 2023"

<https://proxy1-bib.sdu.dk:2048/login?url=https://ovidsp.ovid.com/ovidweb.cgi?T=JS&NEWS=N&PAGE=main&SHAREDSEARCHID=6aI xvZ31INAXy287cbvi5HoWD5amDqG1mxZppJpGCuGjhBEOPwv9FGnwDixAqteXd>

PsycInfo

Link:

[Click to run search](#)

The above Jumpstart will only work for users who have access to this specific database.

Database:

APA PsycInfo <1806 to May Week 1 2023>

#	Query	Results from 10 May 2023
1	laminectomy.mp.	284
2	(dissectom* or diskectom*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	114
3	(surg* adj3 decompression*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	353
4	(spin* adj3 fusion*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	177
5	neurosurgery.mp. or exp Neurosurgery/	19,762
6	(neurosurgical adj3 procedure*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	1,310
7	orthop?edic*.mp.	3,564
8	(spin* adj3 surg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	544
9	(back adj3 pain).mp. or exp Back Pain/ or (low adj3 back adj3 pain).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	7,544
10	radicul*.mp.	674
11	(spin* adj3 disease*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	1,057
12	exp Spinal Column/ or (spin* adj3 column*).mp. or spine.mp. [mp=title, abstract,	7,235

	heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	
13	(lumbar adj3 vertebra*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	680
14	9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13	15,736
15	((spine* or spinal* or lumbar*) adj7 (surg* or neurosurg* or orthop?ed*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	1,257
16	telemedicine*.mp. or exp Telemedicine/ or telehealth*.mp. or tele-health*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	15,532
17	exp Telephone Systems/ or telephone*.mp. or (cell adj3 phone*).mp. or mobile phone*.mp. or exp Mobile Phones/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	40,380
18	exp Smartphones/ or smartphone*.mp. or smart-phone*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	7,784
19	exp Tablet Computers/ or tablet*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	6,265
20	exp Mobile Applications/ or (mobile adj3 application*).mp.	4,502
21	(tele-rehabilitation* or telerehabilitation* or (tele adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Telerehabilitation/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	388
22	telenurs*.mp.	121
23	((video adj3 conf*) or video-conf* or videoconf*).mp. or exp Videoconferencing/	3,473
24	((health adj3 communica*) or (medic* adj3 inform*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	14,481
25	exp "Information and Communication Technology"/ or (informat* adj3 communicat*	216,115

	adj3 techn*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	
26	(informatic* adj3 application*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	169
27	exp Health Information Technology/ or (health adj3 informat* adj3 techn*).mp. or (nurs* adj3 inform*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	8,824
28	(exp Electronic Health Services/ or (electronic adj3 health adj3 service*).mp. or ehealth.mp. or e-health.mp.) adj5 (communicat*.mp. or exp Interpersonal Communication/) [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	3,276
29	((home adj3 visit*) or (house adj3 call*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	6,600
30	(real-time adj3 support*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	219
31	exp Aftercare/ or (after adj3 car*).mp. or after-car*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	10,954
32	((continuo* adj3 nurs*) or (followup adj3 car*) or (follow-up adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	3,311
33	((followup adj3 support*) or (follow-up adj3 support*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	1,185
34	(remote adj3 monitor*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	404
35	(active adj3 post-discharge adj3 surveillanc*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading	0

	word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	
36	exp Simulation/ or simulation*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	111,822
37	((instruction* adj3 film*) or (instruction* adj3 video*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	2,559
38	(pain adj3 manag*).mp. or exp Pain Management/	18,407
39	analgesia*.mp. or exp Analgesia/	9,261
40	(clinic* adj3 teach* adj3 method*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	119
41	(client* adj3 educat*).mp. or exp Client Education/ or (patient* adj3 educat*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	21,620
42	((patient* adj3 car*) or (car* adj3 behavior*)).mp. or exp Caring Behaviors/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	101,806
43	self-car*.mp. or exp Self-Care/ or (self adj3 car*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	29,309
44	(health adj3 promot*).mp. or exp Health Promotion/	54,418
45	((multi-discliplin* adj3 car*) or (multidisciplin adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	0
46	(self-manag* or (self adj3 manag*)).mp. or exp Self-Management/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	19,389
47	recover*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	99,988
48	exp Rehabilitation/ or rehab*.mp. or convalescence.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading	95,636

	word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	
49	(mobile adj3 team\$).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	276
50	exp Text Messaging/ or (text adj3 messag*).mp.	3,891
51	((pre-operative adj3 educat*) or (preoperative adj3 educat*) or (preoperative adj3 exercise*) or (pre-operative adj3 exercise*) or prehabilitation).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	187
52	(emotional adj3 adjust*).mp. or exp Emotional Adjustment/ or (psychologic* adj3 adjust*).mp. or (adapt* adj3 psychologic*).mp. or (physiologic* adj3 adjust*).mp. or (adapt* adj3 physiologic*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	81,100
53	(adaptive adj3 behavior*).mp. or exp Adaptive Behavior/	14,702
54	((short adj3 time adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 term adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 time adj3 hospitalization*) or (short adj3 term adj3 hospitalization*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	293
55	(return* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	2,644
56	(hospital* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	3,153
57	exp Hospital Discharge/ or discharg*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	42,328
58	(postdischarg* or (post adj3 discharg*) or post-discharg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	3,018
59	(transition* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	1,053

60	(length* adj3 stay*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	11,065
61	1 or 2 or 3 or 4	859
62	5 or 6 or 7 or 8	24,497
63	14 and 62	832
64	15 or 61 or 63	2,235
65	16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 or 53	811,175
66	((postoperativ* adj3 rehabilitation*) or (postoperativ* adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	123
67	54 or 55 or 56 or 57 or 58 or 59 or 60 or 66	56,097
68	64 and 65 and 67	68
69	limit 68 to (danish or english or norwegian or swedish)	67
70	limit 69 to yr="2022 - 2023"	3
71	from 70 keep 1-3	3

laminectomy.mp.

(dissectom* or diskectom*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

(surg* adj3 decompression*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

(spin* adj3 fusion*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

neurosurgery.mp. or exp Neurosurgery/

(neurosurgical adj3 procedure*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

orthop?edic*.mp.

(spin* adj3 surg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

(back adj3 pain).mp. or exp Back Pain/ or (low adj3 back adj3 pain).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

radicul*.mp.

(spin* adj3 disease*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

exp Spinal Column/ or (spin* adj3 column*).mp. or spine.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

(lumbar adj3 vertebra*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts,

original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13

((spine* or spinal* or lumbar*) adj7 (surg* or neurosurg* or orthop?ed*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

telemedicine*.mp. or exp Telemedicine/ or telehealth*.mp. or tele-health*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

exp Telephone Systems/ or telephone*.mp. or (cell adj3 phone*).mp. or mobile phone*.mp. or exp Mobile Phones/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

exp Smartphones/ or smartphone*.mp. or smart-phone*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

exp Tablet Computers/ or tablet*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

exp Mobile Applications/ or (mobile adj3 application*).mp.

(tele-rehabilitation* or telerehabilitation* or (tele adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Telerehabilitation/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

telenurs*.mp.

((video adj3 conf*) or video-conf* or videoconf*).mp. or exp Videoconferencing/

((health adj3 communica*) or (medic* adj3 inform*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

exp "Information and Communication Technology"/ or (informat* adj3 communicat* adj3 techn*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

(informatic* adj3 application*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

exp Health Information Technology/ or (health adj3 informat* adj3 techn*).mp. or (nurs* adj3 inform*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

(exp Electronic Health Services/ or (electronic adj3 health adj3 service*).mp. or ehealth.mp. or e-health.mp.) adj5 (communicat*.mp. or exp Interpersonal Communication/) [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

((home adj3 visit*) or (house adj3 call*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

(real-time adj3 support*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

exp Aftercare/ or (after adj3 car*).mp. or after-car*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

((continuo* adj3 nurs*) or (followup adj3 car*) or (follow-up adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

((followup adj3 support*) or (follow-up adj3 support*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

(remote adj3 monitor*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

(active adj3 post-discharge adj3 surveillanc*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

exp Simulation/ or simulation*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

((instruction* adj3 film*) or (instruction* adj3 video*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 (pain adj3 manag*).mp. or exp Pain Management/
 analgesia*.mp. or exp Analgesia/
 (clinic* adj3 teach* adj3 method*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 (client* adj3 educat*).mp. or exp Client Education/ or (patient* adj3 educat*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 ((patient* adj3 car*) or (car* adj3 behavior*)).mp. or exp Caring Behaviors/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 self-car*.mp. or exp Self-Care/ or (self adj3 car*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 (health adj3 promot*).mp. or exp Health Promotion/
 ((multi-discliplin* adj3 car*) or (multidisciplin adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 (self-manag* or (self adj3 manag*)).mp. or exp Self-Management/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 recover*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 exp Rehabilitation/ or rehab*.mp. or convalescence.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 (mobile adj3 team\$).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 exp Text Messaging/ or (text adj3 messag*).mp.
 ((pre-operative adj3 educat*) or (preoperative adj3 educat*) or (preoperative adj3 exercise*) or (pre-operative adj3 exercise*) or prehabilitation).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 (emotional adj3 adjust*).mp. or exp Emotional Adjustment/ or (psychologic* adj3 adjust*).mp. or (adapt* adj3 psychologic*).mp. or (physiologic* adj3 adjust*).mp. or (adapt* adj3 physiologic*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 (adaptive adj3 behavior*).mp. or exp Adaptive Behavior/
 ((short adj3 time adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 term adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 time adj3 hospitalization*) or (short adj3 term adj3 hospitalization*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 (return* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 (hospital* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 exp Hospital Discharge/ or discharg*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 (postdischarg* or (post adj3 discharg*) or post-discharg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 (transition* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
 (length* adj3 stay*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

1 or 2 or 3 or 4

5 or 6 or 7 or 8

14 and 62

15 or 61 or 63

16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 or 53

((postoperativ* adj3 rehabilitation*) or (post-operativ* adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]

54 or 55 or 56 or 57 or 58 or 59 or 60 or 66

64 and 65 and 67

limit 68 to (danish or english or norwegian or swedish)

limit 69 to yr="2022 - 2023"

from 70 keep 1-3

<https://proxy1-bib.sdu.dk:2048/login?url=https://ovidsp.ovid.com/ovidweb.cgi?T=JS&NEWS=N&PAGE=main&SHAREDSEARCHID=4zQ1qbWPWG2c7pxbrNfPrOxC0LYK9e6R9NI9AlCW9xL5jRUSXKtvRD8wxDaZPHUgF>

Scopus

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416 document results

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( TITLE-ABS-KEY ( ( laminectomy OR "Discectomy, Percutaneous" OR discectom* OR
dissectom* OR ( surg* W/3 decompression* ) OR ( spin* W/3 fusion* ) ) OR ( (
"Neurosurgery" OR ( neurosurgical W/3 procedure* ) OR orthop?edic* OR ( spin* W/3
surg* ) ) AND ( ( back W/3 pain ) OR ( low W/3 back W/3 pain ) OR radicul* OR ( spin*
W/3 disease* ) OR ( spine* W/3 column* ) OR ( lumbar W/3 vertebra* ) ) ) OR ( ( spine*
OR spinal* OR lumbar* ) W/7 ( surg* OR neurosurg* OR orthop?ed* ) ) ) ) AND ( (
TITLE-ABS-KEY ( ( telemedicine* OR telehealth* OR tele-health* OR telephone* OR ( cell*
W/3 phone* ) OR ( mobile W/3 phone* ) OR smartphone* OR smart-phone* OR tablet*
OR ( mobile W/3 application* ) OR telerehabilitation* OR ( tele W/3 rehabilitation* ) OR
telenurs* OR videoconf* OR video-conf* OR ( video W/3 conf* ) OR ( health W/3
communica* ) OR ( medic* W/3 inform* ) OR ( inform* W/3 communicat* W/3 techn* )
OR ( inform* W/3 application* ) OR ( nurs* W/3 inform* ) OR ( health W/3 inform* W/3
tech* ) OR ( ( ( electronic W/3 health W/3 service* ) OR ehealth OR e-health ) W/5 (
communicat* ) ) ) ) ) OR ( TITLE-ABS-KEY ( ( ( home W/3 visit* ) OR ( house W/3 call* )
OR ( real-time W/3 support* ) OR ( after W/3 car* ) OR after-car* OR ( followup W/3 car*
) OR ( continuo* W/3 nurs* ) OR ( follow-up W/3 car* ) OR ( followup W/3 support* ) OR
( follow-up W/3 support* ) OR ( remote W/3 monitor* ) OR ( active W/3 post-discharg*
W/3 surveillanc* ) OR simulation* OR ( instruction* W/3 film* ) OR ( instruction* W/3
video* ) OR analgesia* OR ( pain W/3 manag* ) OR ( clinic* W/3 teach* W/3 method* )
OR ( patient* W/3 educat* ) OR ( patient* W/3 car* ) OR self-car* OR ( self W/3 car* )
OR ( health W/3 promot* ) OR ( multi-disciplin* W/3 car* ) OR ( multidisciplin* W/3 car* )
OR self-manag* OR ( self W/3 manag* ) OR recover* OR convalescence* OR rehab* OR (
mobile W/3 team$ ) OR ( text W/3 messag* ) OR ( pre-operative W/3 educat* ) OR (
preoperative W/3 educat* ) OR ( preoperative W/3 exercise* ) OR ( pre-operative W/3
exercise* ) OR prehabilitation* OR ( emotional W/3 adjust* ) OR ( adaptive W/3 behav* )
OR ( psychologic* W/3 adjust* ) OR ( adapt* W/3 psychologic* ) OR ( physiologic* W/3
adjust* ) OR ( adapt* W/3 physiologic* ) ) ) ) ) AND ( TITLE-ABS-KEY ( ( ( short W/3 time
W/3 stay* ) OR ( short W/3 term W/3 stay* ) OR ( short W/3 time W/3 hospitalization* )
OR ( short W/3 term W/3 hospitalization AND * ) OR ( return* W/3 home* ) OR (
hospital* W/3 home* ) OR discharg* OR postdischarg* OR ( post W/3 discharg* ) OR post-
discharg* OR ( postoperativ* W/3 rehabilitation* ) OR ( post-operativ* W/3 rehabilitation* )
OR ( transition* W/3 home* ) OR ( length* W/3 stay* ) ) ) ) ) AND ORIG-LOAD-DATE AFT
20220324 AND ( LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE , "English" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE ,
"Danish" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE , "Norwegian" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE ,
"Swedish" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2023 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR , 2022 ) ) )
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